

MATHEW MANNAPARAMBIL

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Abstract: Mathew Mannaparambil SJ (1948-1980) witnesses to Jesus by building a Christian community in Sasaram, Bihar, inspired by the *koinōnia* of Jesus' early disciples (cf. Acts 2:42). As a true pastor, like Jesus the good shepherd, Mathew spends his life totally for his people. Responding to injustice and driven by a prophetic desire to build God's reign, his pastoral heart seeks to walk with his people lovingly. His blood shed in Sasaram helps God's reign evolve today. His martyrdom continues to bear fruit in terms of integral development through *koinōnia*.

Keywords: Mathew Mannaparambil, Community, Communion, *koinōnia*, Jesus-Witness, God's Kingdom

INTRODUCTION

This series, titled "GOSPEL in ACTION," sheds light on Jesus' witnesses who by their deeds culminating in the "pouring out of blood" (cf. Lk 22:20) testify to the good news of the risen Lord Jesus Christ.¹ Mathew Mannaparambil SJ (1948-1980)

¹ The twelve Jesus-witnesses introduced in the Series "GOSPEL in ACTION" in 2026 are: Devasahayam, Rani Maria, Kandhamal martyrs, Herman Rasschaert, Mathew Mannaparambil, Anthony Murmu, James Kottayil, Stan Swamy, Arul Doss, AT Thomas, Valsa John, and Tom Gafney. Each of these twelve proclaims the Gospel with a Spirit-guided praxis. The *Acts of the Apostles* and *When the Gospel Grows Feet*, a biography on Rutilio Grande, inspire the series-title "GOSPEL in ACTION." In presenting each Jesus-witness, there is (1) a brief introduction to the martyr and their contextual Gospel praxis, and (2) a concise exposition to a defining characteristic of witnessing (*martyria*).

witnesses to Jesus by nurturing a community of believers in Sasaram, Bihar, based on genuine love and sharing. As a shepherd of his people, like Jesus the good shepherd, he spends his life totally for his people.

1. NURTURING JESUS' COMMUNITY

The ultimate conviction of Mathew Mannaparambil expressed in the following words describes his desire to love as Jesus loves and to pay its price.

The following of Christ may eventually lead us to a final identification with Christ in his death on the cross. But we know Christ rose from the dead and is present in us and with us. This victory of Christ will give us the strength and the courage to face even death, in loving and serving others even to the point of death.²

For Mathew, “the mismanagement and corruption going on in the [Sasaram] mission was not just a matter of money. It was also the question of justice and moral responsibility.”³ He notices that the resources “meant to build up the mission, particularly the poor Christian community” are not channeled properly, and instead are “plundered by dishonest persons for their life of luxury.”⁴ His efforts in responding to this “injustice done to both the donors and to the poor

² These parting words of Mathew Mannaparambil, a few moments before his murder on 7 March 1980, are recorded in a circular letter written by Abraham Puthumana SJ, Patna Jesuit Provincial (1977-1982), on 11 March 1980. Cf. Abraham Puthumana SJ, “Some Reflections on the Occasion of the Death of Fr. Mathew Mannaparambil, S.J. at the hands of assailants” (Patna: Patna Jesuit Archives), 1. See also Henry P. Oiz, *Blessed by the Lord: A History of Patna Jesuits, 1921-1981* (Patna: Patna Jesuit Society, 1991), 353.

³ Sudha Varghese SND, “Mathew Mannaparambil: A Voice against Dishonesty and Disloyalty,” *Jivan* (November 2020): 22. Padmashri Sudha SND, a social activist and director of Prerana Hostel for Musahar girls, contends that, despite the dream of the founder of Sasaram mission, Joseph Mann SJ, to build up an ideal Christian community in a remote place in Bihar with about 100 villages where regular evangelical work was going on, there were mismanagement and corruption due to the improper accountability of some of the lay mission staff.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 23.

beneficiaries” climax in his murder on 7 March 1980. Thus, he is a martyr “who sacrificed his life for justice, honesty and integrity.”⁵

“The simmering of love from Fr. Mathew’s tomb stirred the missionary spirit in his followers.”⁶ He is entombed at the portal of the Sasaram church. “The reasoning was that the meaning of his life and death would best be brought out by the presence of his mortal remains where he was murdered.”⁷ The villagers admire his boldness in facing challenges in the mission. They share that “[we] disagreed with Fr. Matthew in many ways, but he wanted our lasting good he gave us light – we are proud of him.”⁸ His martyrdom entails “much introspection in the Church circles which resulted in the re-orientation of mission work in Patna Church. There was a renewed determination to continue the work of evangelization at Sasaram.”⁹

“I have the firm faith that Mathew’s blood has not been shed in vain, and that he will direct things in Sasaram, and new life will emerge,” these hope-filled words of Amala SND have come true. Her words have inspired many Notre Dame sisters to dedicate themselves “to begin anew” in Sasaram.¹⁰ Three SNDs, Sujita, Reeta, and Sabeena volunteer “to be the new Team to return to Sasaram for whatever the Lord had in

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Joseph Velamkunel SJ, “The Withering of the Banyan Tree: The Closing of the Mission,” in *A Historical Survey of Sasaram Mission: Diamond Jubilee 1956-2016*, ed. Joseph Velamkunel (Patna: Patna Jesuit Archives, 2016), 33. Velamkunel affirms that “the simmering of love from the tomb continued to animate the contours of a new mission in Sasaram.” Ibid., 26.

⁷ Ibid., 26.

⁸ Ibid., 25.

⁹ Jose Kalapura, “Tested, Tried, and Transformed Patna Church: A Study of the Martyrdom of Mathew Mannaparambil SJ – Part I,” *VJTR* 89/5 (May 2025): 351.

¹⁰ Cf. SND Patna Newsletter (Easter 1980), 2. Affirming that “Mathew has been called to witness to his missionary vocation,” Mary Amala SND, the Notre Dame provincial in 1980, invites her sisters to introspect their “missionary identity” and to evaluate their “way of sharing material goods” with the people in the mission.

mind for the mission” and arrive Sasaram on 31 July 1980.¹¹ Sujita SND recounts that “while sharing about Fr. Mathew, several persons, especially the catechists, praised him for his dedication and love, his wonderful organizational abilities, his courage and his commitment to the mission.”¹²

Acknowledging his own “sorrow and grief at the untimely death of a brother and a friend, along with anger bordering on vengeance against the perpetrators of such a heinous crime,” Abraham Puthumana SJ shares that

after seeing the serene, peaceful, almost smiling face of Fr. Mathew lying dead in his room and praying and reflecting on his own last instruction, a completely different emotion has begun to envelop me. I feel a great calm and peace within me. The over-riding thought in my mind now is that Fr. Mathew has died a martyr’s death. His death will not go in vain. The greatest testimony to a man’s profession of love and concern for fellowmen is to testify to one’s profession by laying down one’s own life as Fr. Mathew has done for Sasaram.¹³

¹¹ Cf. Sujita SND, “Sasaram Mission: From Death to New Life,” in *A Historical Survey of Sasaram Mission*, 91. In her “reflections focused on the developments in the Sasaram mission after the martyrdom of Mathew Mannaparambil on 7 March 1980 until January 1984,” Sujita SND asks a fundamental question: “How are we to turn the power of this experience of the cross of Fr. Mathew’s martyrdom toward new life for the mission?” Ibid. She narrates that “from August 3rd on, we began our pilgrim journey, moving from village to village, carrying a small cloth bag with what was absolutely necessary for us, and taking one day at a time, trusting in the providence of God and the goodness of our people. As I look back on those 5-6 months of wandering in the remote villages of the then Shahpur District, conducting meetings with our people and listening to them, depending on them for our food and security, experiencing their warm hospitality most of the time and, at other times, being confronted with total rejection, I realize that in this process, our hearts went through an experience of growing larger and more compassionate and more willing to listen and to learn from our people. In retrospect, I can see that this was one of the most apostolically challenging and fruitful experiences of my religious life and to this day I count it as a great grace and a gift given to me by God.” Ibid., 94.

¹² Sujita SND, “Sasaram Mission,” 96.

¹³ Puthumana, “Some Reflections on the Occasion of the Death of Fr. Mathew Mannaparambil,” 3.

Mathew's death has not gone in vain. Today, after 45 years of his blood being "poured out," there is new life and a growing community in Sasaram. Navjeevan (literally, 'new life') Health Centre animated by Notre Dame Sisters in Sasaram, with a resident medical doctor, caters to hundreds of villagers, especially women, and it assists in their holistic wellbeing, community-health and hygiene. After being closed for 21 years since Mathew's martyrdom, St. Anne's School resumed in January 2001. Administered by Patna Jesuits, it offers integral education to 1235 students with the support of 33 teachers.¹⁴ There are also pastoral and social ministries where the Notre Dame Sisters, Jesuits, and lay animators collaborate to evolve an egalitarian society.¹⁵ A seed falls to the ground, it dies, and it produces fruit (cf. Jn 12:24). So does the Lord allow the blood of martyr Mathew to be poured out and to produce new life and a renewed community in Sasaram.

2. *KOINŌNIA* (COMMUNION)

Jesus' witness to the Father through his ministry is oriented to forming a new communion (*koinōnia*) of disciples. The

¹⁴ Cf. "Educational Statistics of Patna Province," *Catalogue of the Patna Jesuit Province 2026*, 197. Besides St. Anne's School situated in Burhan, where the Sasaram mission was started by Joseph Mann in 1956, there are two village schools at Kalashahar and Ramdihara with 114 and 176 students respectively with seven teachers each. Am grateful to Albert Abraham SJ, who heads St. Anne's currently, for providing me with helpful documents on the educational activities of the Sasaram mission. On the process of starting the Ramdihara village school by the people on 26 January 1982, Joseph Srampikal SJ reminisces that he "put up a hut for the children to sit and study. All able-bodied people decided to go up the Rohtas Hills and bring down the needed bamboos and another day go across the Sone river and bring the grass for the roof. In two months' time the cottage was ready and a teacher and myself began to teach there." Joseph Srampikal SJ, "My Experiences at Sasaram," in *A Historical Survey of Sasaram Mission*, 108-109.

¹⁵ Rural Educational and Associated Programme (REAP), in Sasaram, facilitates non-formal education and self-help groups. "Innovative Education Programme" for the Musahars, a marginalized community identified as extremely backward (*mahadalit*) in Bihar, has helped in educating many first-generation learners.

earliest use of the term *koinōnia* in Acts is in 2:42 where Luke refers to such a new communion of disciples who devote “to the apostles’ teaching and fellowship (*koinōnia*), and to the breaking of bread and the prayers.” It is the fulfilment of Jesus’ prayer: “Father, hallowed be your name. Your kingdom come. Give us each day our daily bread...” (Lk 11:2-3). The proclamation and actualization of the Father’s kingdom begin with Jesus and are continued in the witness of his disciples.¹⁶ *Koinōnia* in “the sense of table fellowship or communitarian *agapē*” is what Jesus practises in his ministry both in Galilee and Jerusalem.¹⁷ His mighty deeds demonstrate “the reality of God’s in-breaking rule.”¹⁸

Jesus’ *koinōnia* builds inclusive community by breaking down divisions. Forgiveness and shared table fellowship contribute to this new communion. The parable of the Good Samaritan (Lk 10:25-37), the healing of the ten suffering from leprosy (Lk 17:11-19), and rebuking James and John against retaliatory violence on the Samaritan village (Lk 9:51-56) are examples of reconciling Jews and Samaritans. Similarly, the divide between the righteous and sinners is narrowed down by the call of Levi (Lk 5:27-32) and the visit to Zacchaeus (Lk

¹⁶ Jesus testifies to the Father through his ministry that unfolds the kingdom. About God’s kingdom, Joel D. Fredrich comments that “we possess it now and will enjoy its future glory through faith in the gospel of Jesus. Already in Mark 1:15 we hear Jesus proclaim, ‘The time has come. The Kingdom of God is near. Repent and believe the good news!’ The rest of his ministry makes it ever clearer that the good news is good news *about him* and that the blessings of the kingdom are received through faith *in him*.” Joel D. Fredrich, “The Lord’s Prayer: Exegesis of Matthew 6:9-13 and Luke 11:2-4,” *Wisconsin Lutheran Quarterly* 107/4 (Fall 2010): 263 (emphasis in the original).

¹⁷ Cf. George Panikulam, *Koinōnia in the New Testament: A Dynamic Expression of Christian Life*, *Analeceta Biblica* 85 (Rome: Biblical Institute Press, 1979), 123.

¹⁸ J. Bradley Chance, *Acts*, Smyth & Helwys Bible Commentary 23 (Macon, GA: Smyth & Helwys Publishing, 2007), 59. Besides the “signs and wonders” carried out both by Jesus and the Apostles, according to Chance, “the community was devoted to ‘fellowship’ (v. 42). At the root of the word *koinōnia* is the idea of sharing. While Christian fellowship can take on many characteristics, in this context such sharing manifests itself in the early community’s practice of having all things in common (*koina*, v. 44).” *Ibid.*

19:1-10). Jesus' table fellowship, i.e., eating with tax collectors, sinners, Pharisees, and disciples, becomes a foretaste of the messianic banquet. His ultimate act of reconciling love from the cross extends forgiveness even to the executioners (Lk 23:34). Thus, his *koinōnia* demonstrates the inclusive reach of the Father's reconciling love.

Mathew Mannaparambil's response to Lord Jesus in Sasaram mission involves the formation and growth of community through "participation and communion" (*koinōnia*).¹⁹ Confronted by dishonesty and corruption in the Sasaram community, its pastor seeks to redress the conflict through communitarian deliberation that involves the catechists and collaborators of the mission. This adaptation of the "Jerusalem model" of the early church, in the form of the Indian practice of *satsaṅg* (communion), is beneficial for collective deliberation and effective execution.²⁰ The pilgrim steps of the "Sasaram Team," that involves listening to needs and desires of the people of Sasaram, is akin to Jerusalem's "congregational gathering" (*satsaṅg*) under the guidance of Jesus, the Sadguru. It is a model for breaking linguistic-cultural barriers that challenge equity and inclusion.²¹ The communitarian deliberations and listening that *satsaṅg* promotes makes it relevant for generous sharing and reconciliatory crisis-resolution.

¹⁹ In the absolute, *koinōnia* means "fellowship." However, according to Hauck, "in Ac. 2:42 *koinōnia* does not denote the concrete community or society of Christians which, while it had not yet separated itself legally and culturally from the Jewish community, already represented a circle of the closest fellowship. Nor can it signify the community of goods (cf. v. 44). It is rather an abstract and spiritual term for the fellowship of brotherly concord established and expressed in the life of the community." Friedrich Hauck, "*koinōnia*," *TDNT*, 3:809.

²⁰ The Sanskrit word *satsaṅg/satsaṅga* is derived from the roots *sát* and *saṅga* and means "association with the good." Cf. Monier-Williams, "*sát*," in *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, 1134-1135.

²¹ *Satsaṅg*'s practice of learning from a Guru "who would help to be with the truth" has the potential for a Jesus-disciple, who follows Jesus the Sadguru, to adapt the practice integrating sharing and fellowship in the Indian context. Cf. Natasha Dalmia, *Practice of Satsaṅg: Conscious Living – Celebrating the Truth of Who You Are* (Singapore: Patridge, 2014), 15.

CONCLUSION

Witnessing to the gospel of Lord Jesus Christ, Mathew Mannaparambil remains a steward of the Kingdom community. Responding to injustice, and driven by a desire to build God's reign, his pastoral heart seeks to walk with his people and to foster a *koinōnia* of love and justice. In this mission, he imitates Jesus the good shepherd who lays down his life for his own that new life emerges. His blood shed in Sasaram testifies to God's reign that is still evolving. His martyrdom continues to bear fruit in terms of fellowship, justice, and integral development.

Excerpt taken from the Documents of the Third General Conference of Latin American Bishops, Puebla, 1979.

“The poor deserve preferential attention, whatever their moral or personal situation. They have been made in the image and likeness of God to be his children, but this image has been obscured and even violated. For this reason, God has become their defender and loves them. It follows that the poor are those to whom the mission is first addressed, and their evangelization is par excellence the sign and proof of the mission of Jesus.”

Excerpt taken from Parmananda Divarkar, “Future of Mission in Asia,” in *A New Missionary Era*, ed. Padraig Flanagan, SPS, Maryknoll, NY: Orbis, 1982.

“In any true dialogue as in true love, there is dying to self until one finds oneself more fully in that other. In a true dialogue between Gospel and a particular culture it may sometimes be that the word of God is lost or put in danger, but in fact it finds itself more fully.”